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AN APPRECIATION OF LOUIS-RENÉ MATOUT, BECQUEREL'S ASSISTANT

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Abstract: Louis-René Matout (1869-1944) was a French researcher who worked both with Henri Becquerel (1852-1908) and his son Jean Becquerel (1878-1953) at the National History Museum, in Paris. Initially as a *préparateur* of the Physics laboratory, afterwards as an assistant, for almost 40 years he participated in the researches developed at the Museum. Besides aiding the investigations led by Henri and Jean Becquerel, he also had an independent scientific production and he became a well-known physicist, in the early twentieth century. This article offers a view of his career, also discussing the claim that he participated in the discovery of radioactivity.

Keywords: history of physics; history of science; Henri Becquerel; Jean Becquerel; Louis-René Matout; radioactivity

1. INTRODUCTION

The usual approach in history of science gives a lot of attention to the most famous researchers, paying little tribute to the multitude of lesser-known scientists, whose contributions are nevertheless highly relevant. Especially in the case of experimental investigations, a research is seldom an individual activity – it is customarily a group undertaking. This is true today and it was also so one hundred years ago.

This article will spotlight one among many unknown research assistants of the early twentieth century: Louis-René Matout (1869-1944), a French researcher who worked both with Henri Becquerel (1852-1908) and his son Jean Becquerel (1878-1953) at the National History Museum, in Paris. Operating in the shadow of two well-known physicists, mostly viewed as a mere supporter of the researches of the two professors, Louis Matout was nevertheless a capable scientist. He began his career at the Paris *Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle* as a *préparateur* – a position that is usually construed as a humble technical work, but that was much more than that. In principle, he could progress from *préparateur* to assistant, and then from assistant to professor of the chair of Applied Physics at the *Muséum*. He became indeed an assistant, but his career could not proceed further because Jean Becquerel stood on his path.

Louis Matout first aided the investigations led by Henri Becquerel from the late nineteenth century up to his death, in 1908, and afterwards he became the assistant of Jean Becquerel. Besides that, he also had an independent scientific production and published many independent papers and two books on physics. He was also the coauthor of some of Jean Becquerel's

publications. He became a well-known physicist, in the early twentieth century. After World War I, he also engaged into a series of studies about fishes and angling, that resulted in a large number of publications and to the invention of a new fishing line and a special fishing rod.

The website of the Matout family (www.matout.fr) has made public a claim that he participated in the discovery of radioactivity, and that Henri Becquerel shared with him his part of the Nobel Prize in Physics of 1903. This claim, that has emerged a few times, will also be discussed in this paper.

2. DID LOUIS MATOUT DISCOVER RADIOACTIVITY?

On January 25, 1939, the French National Museum of Natural History celebrated the centenary of its Chair of Applied Physics (Anonymous, 1939). Since its foundation, this Chair was occupied successively by four members of the Becquerel family: Antoine-César Becquerel (1788-1878), Alexandre-Edmond Becquerel (1820-1891), Antoine-Henri Becquerel (1852-1908), and Jean-Antoine-Édmond-Marie Becquerel (1878-1953). It is well known that Henri Becquerel's 1896 researches on the radiation emitted by uranium and its compounds – a landmark in the discovery of radioactivity – happened in the laboratory of the *Muséum*, and it was one of the highlights of the commemoration.

The formal celebration ceremony of the centenary of the Physics Chair occurred in the presence of the President of the French Republic, the Minister of National Education and several other authorities and scientists. The discourses of the director of the *Muséum*, Alfred Louis Pierre Germain (1878-1942), and of the fourth physics professor of the *Muséum*, Jean Becquerel (1878-1953), were published soon afterwards (Germain, 1939; Becquerel, 1939).

In the printed version of Germain's address one can find photographs of the members of the Becquerel family, and also of one additional person who is not well known today: Louis-René Matout (1869-1944). Under his photograph (Fig. 1), we can read the caption: "Louis Matout, Henri Becquerel's partner in the discovery of radioactivity" (*Louis Matout, collaborateur d'Henri Becquerel dans la découverte de la radio-activité*) (Germain, 1939, p. 127).

Who was Louis Matout? And what role did he play in the discovery of radioactivity? Hitherto, he has been a shadowy worker who is sometimes mentioned as Henri Becquerel's *préparateur* – a position that will be made more clear below. Of course, Louis Matout did participate in several of Becquerel's experiments, as will be shown in this paper. However, the photograph caption did not simply state that Matout aided Becquerel in his studies concerning radioactivity; the claim is much stronger – let us repeat it: "Louis Matout, Henri Becquerel's partner in the discovery of radioactivity".

Louis MATOUT, collaborateur d'Henri Becquerel
dans la découverte de la radio-activité

Fig. 1. “Louis Matout, Henri Becquerel’s partner in the discovery of radioactivity” (Germain, 1939, p. 127)

This paper will present some relevant (although inconclusive) evidence concerning the role of Louis-René Matout in the discovery of radioactivity. A conclusive assessment of his contribution must wait for the discovery of further documents, as will be shown. This article will offer a description of his scientific career, including both his collaboration with Henri and Jean Becquerel, and his own individual undertakings.

3. THE LETTER OF GAVIN DE BEER

The starting point of my interest on Matout was an unexpected finding in the archives of the Paris *Académie des Sciences*: a letter from Sir Gavin de Beer to Pierre Gauja – who was the chief of the Academy archive – reporting a claim and asking for information about Louis Matout.¹ This letter was written in French; its translation is fully reproduced below.

Dear Sir,

I am sure you will forgive me if I contact you with a minor question on history of science.

Two years ago, in Nyons (Drôme), I made the acquaintance of a Captain Matout,² distinguished Resistant, Maquisard, decorated with the rare medal of Social Merit [*Mérite Social*], who ensured the operation of the “Library for all” in this friendly city.

¹ Archive de l'Académie des Sciences, Paris. Dossier Beer, Sir Gavin de. Letter of Gavin de Beer to Pierre Gauja, March 2 1969.

² Captain Louis-Pierre Matout (1904-1982) organized and commanded a group of maquis. The maquis were rural bands of French Resistance fighters, called *maquisards*, during the Nazi occupation of France in World War II. For his role during the War, in 1948 Louis-Pierre Matout was awarded the “Croix des

He told me that his father had been Henri Becquerel's preparer [*préparateur*] at the Museum at the time when Wilhelm Röntgen published his discovery of X-rays, in 1895. Becquerel, he told me, envisaged an experiment to check if elements like uranium had the property of producing light by fluorescence under the influence of solar rays.³ To this end, he instructed Matout senior to prepare photographic plates containing a uranium salt under the opaque paper,⁴ and to expose the plates to the Sun. Unfortunately, for three days the Sun did not show at all, and Becquerel told Matout to throw away the plates and to prepare new ones, which he did. But, before throwing away the old plates, Matout had the idea of developing them, and he saw the effects of uranium on them. So, was it not Matout who was the first to "see" the testimony of radioactivity? Of course, I don't know if he was able of realizing the significance of what he had seen; and to obtain additional details, I wrote to Captain Matout at Nyons last year; but my letter remained unanswered.

Are you familiar with this little story?

Excuse me again, dear Sir, for disturbing you; I beg you to pay my respects to Madame Gauja and to believe in the expression of my cordially devoted feelings

Gavin de Beer

Pierre Gauja replied one week later.⁵ I reproduce below a partial translation of his letter.

Dear Sir

I took the liberty of showing your letter of the 12th to Mr. Louis de Broglie.

In his opinion, the role of chance and of the preparer [*préparateur*] in the production and observation of the facts which led to the discovery of radioactivity are certain, but it was indeed Henri Becquerel who discovered its true nature.

Nothing in our Archives allows us to doubt it. [...]

Let us briefly identify the participants mentioned in the exchange of letters.

Sir Gavin Rylands de Beer (1899-1972) was a British evolutionary embryologist. Although his parents were British, he spent most of his childhood in France, where he lived until he was 13 years old (Barrington, 1973, p. 65). During this period he learned English from his parents, French at school and German from his Swiss nurse. Later, he studied Zoology in Oxford, where he started his academic career. In 1938 he moved to London, where he taught Zoology, Evolution and Embriology until his retirement in 1960. In 1965 he left England to live in Switzerland, which he usually visited during his vacations (Barrington, 1973, pp. 78-79). Since the decade of 1950 he became much involved with history of science and he studied and edited Charles Darwin's notebooks. He was a Corresponding Member of the Académie des Sciences de l'Institut de France, and in this circumstance he became acquainted with Pierre Gauja. The episode concerning Louis Matout happened during a travel to France, in the period when he was living in Switzerland. Due to his early education, he was able to communicate very well in French. Gavin de Beer returned to England in 1971 and he died in Sussex the next year.

Pierre Gauja (aprox. 1890-1969) was originally an engineer of arts and manufactures. For some unknown personal circumstances, he was charged with the organization of the Archive of

services militaires volontaires", or Voluntary Military Service Cross (*Journal Officiel de la République Française. Lois et décrets*, 31 May 1948, p. 5240).

³ "[...] avaient la propriété de produire de la lumière par fluorescence sous l'influence des rayons solaires". The meaning of this remark is that Becquerel was looking for some invisible radiation, similar to X-rays, that could be produced by the excitation of luminescent material.

⁴ "[...] préparer des plaques photographiques contenant un sel d'uranium sous le papier opaque [...]". As a matter of fact, the photographic plates were wrapped in opaque paper, and the luminescent material was placed outside, over it.

⁵ Archive de l'Académie des Sciences, Paris. Fonds Henri Becquerel. Letter of Pierre Gauja to Mr. Gavin de Beer, March 19 1969.

the *Académie des Sciences* by Alfred Lacroix, when the later became the secretary of the Academy in 1914 (Saunders, 1978, p. 699; Bret, 2011, p. 167). Gauja became deeply involved with the documentation and he wrote several books and papers on the history of the Academy. He worked for 55 years as the Chief Secretary at that institution and he died in August 1969 (Tardi, 1970, p. 21), a few months after the exchange of letters concerning Louis Matout. Hence, there was no follow-up of this transaction.

At the time of this exchange of letters, Jean Becquerel (Henri's son) had already passed away (in 1953). Louis Matout had died in 1944. It was impossible, therefore, to obtain further information from them. It is unlikely that Gauja searched for evidence about Matout in the Archives of the Academy of Science, because he already knew that no information would be found there.

In his reply to Gavin de Beer, Pierre Gauja's mentioned that he had brought the subject to the attention of Louis de Broglie (1892-1987), the famous physicist who introduced the wave properties of the electron. De Broglie was Life Secretary (*Sécretaire Perpétuel*) of the French Academy of Sciences from 1942 to 1975, when he resigned (Abragan, 1988, p. 38). Gauja's demand of his opinion was, therefore, an understandable move.

4. BECQUEREL'S EARLY EXPERIMENTS

Let us now return to the core of the exchange of letters between Gavin de Beer and Pierre Gauja. What could be the relevance of the claim presented by Louis Matout's son? It is important to understand the history of Henri Becquerel's researches.

Becquerel's presented to the Academy of Science his first communication on uranium radiation on the 24th February 1896. His short note stated that, using a photographic plate covered by opaque paper, he detected a penetrating radiation emitted by a phosphorescent substance (double sulphate of uranyl and potassium) that was kept under sunlight (Becquerel, 1896a).

A Lumière photographic plate, with gelatine-bromide [of silver], is wrapped with two sheets of very thick black paper, such that the plate is not veiled by exposure to the Sun, for a whole day.

Over the sheet of paper, outside, a plate of the phosphorescent substance is put, and the whole is exposed to the Sun, for several hours. When the photographic plate is developed afterwards, we recognize that the silhouette of the phosphorescent substance appears in black on the cliché. If one interposes a coin, or a pierced metallic screen, between the phosphorescent substance and the paper, one sees the image of these objects appearing on the photograph.

We can repeat the same experiments by interposing between the phosphorescent substance and the paper a thin glass slide, which excludes the possibility of a chemical action due to vapours which could emanate from the substance heated by the solar rays.

We must therefore conclude from these experiments that the phosphorescent substance in question emits radiations which pass through the paper that is opaque to light, and reduce the silver salts. (Becquerel, 1896a, p. 421)

The experiment he made was an adaptation of those that had been reported by Charles Henri (1896) and by Gaston Henri Niewenglowski (1896) in the previous weeks. They had detected penetrating radiation emitted by other phosphorescent substances (zinc sulphide and calcium sulphide) under similar conditions. The motivation of all those investigations was Poincaré's conjecture that luminescent substances could emit X-rays (Poincaré, 1896, p. 56; see Martins, 2021a). In the specific case of the substance used by Henri Becquerel, the phosphorescence is very short-lived; since the experiment required a long exposition (several hours) of the photographic plate to the invisible radiation, the initial expectation was that the experiment could only succeed if the arrangement was kept under sunlight during a long time.

Becquerel read his second communication to the Academy one week later, on 2nd March 1896. He reported that the radiation emitted by his samples was able to pass through thin metal plates. He also observed that his samples of double sulphate of uranyl and potassium emitted penetrating radiation even when kept in the dark. He remarked that the visible phosphorescence of those samples is very short (1/100 s) – therefore, the phenomenon was not associated with common phosphorescence. He proposed the hypothesis that the phenomenon was produced by radiations similar to X-rays emitted by phosphorescence, with a persistence much larger than that of visible phosphorescence of the same substance (Becquerel, 1896b).

I will particularly insist on the following fact, which seems to me quite important and distant from the phenomena that one could expect to observe: The same crystalline lamellae, placed in front of photographic plates, under the same conditions and with the same screens, but shielded from the excitement of incident radiation and kept in the dark, still produce the same photographic impressions. Here is how I was led to make this observation: Among the preceding experiments, some had been prepared on Wednesday 26 and Thursday 27 February and, because on those days the sun only showed itself of intermittently, I have kept the experiments all prepared and I put the devices in the dark in a cabinet drawer, leaving the lamellae of the uranium salt in place. As the sun did not show again on the following days, I developed the photographic plates on March 1, expecting to find very faint images. The silhouettes appeared, on the contrary, with great intensity. (Becquerel, 1896b, p. 502)

Although Henri Becquerel did not claim, in this second paper, that he had discovered a completely new phenomenon, it is usually supposed that the observation of a penetrating radiation emitted independently of visible luminescence was a fundamental step in the discovery of radioactivity. And this is exactly the step associated to the claim presented by Louis Matout's son, as was reported above:⁶

Becquerel, he told me, envisaged an experiment to check if elements like uranium had the property of producing light by fluorescence under the influence of solar rays. To this end, he instructed Matout senior to prepare photographic plates containing a uranium salt under the opaque paper, and to expose the plates to the Sun. Unfortunately, for three days the Sun did not show at all, and Becquerel told Matout to throw away the plates and to prepare new ones, which he did. But, before throwing away the old plates, Matout had the idea of developing them, and he saw the effects of uranium on them.

Notice that the language employed by Becquerel in his publication does not suggest that anyone else participated in his experiments. The whole description uses the pronoun “je” to point out who did the operations: “I was led to make this observation” (*j'ai été conduit à faire cette observation*), “I have kept the experiments all prepared and I put the devices in the dark in a cabinet drawer” (*j'avais conservé les expériences toutes préparées et rentré les châssis à l'obscurité dans le tiroir d'un meuble*), “I developed the photographic plates” (*j'ai développé les plaques photographiques*).

Of course, Becquerel's omission of the name of any person who might have aided him is fully understandable, in the circumstances of that time. Laboratory personnel were seldom mentioned in the scientific publications. We do know that Louis Matout helped Becquerel during many years. However, in his 1903 book where he summarized all his contributions to radioactivity, Becquerel mentioned Louis Matout only once (Becquerel, 1903, p. 267) – and at this place, he did not acknowledge his help in his investigations, but mentioned Matout's own experiments on the action of radiation upon seeds. We should also notice that Henri Becquerel

⁶ Archive de l'Académie des Sciences, Paris. Dossier Beer, Sir Gavin de. Letter of Gavin de Beer to Pierre Gauja, March 2 1969.

was usually unwilling to give credit to other researchers, concerning radioactivity (Martins, 2021).

Becquerel's unpublished manuscripts do not provide any additional information, except for a very odd circumstance concerning his two first articles. Henri Becquerel systematically registered his laboratory activities in a series of notebooks.⁷ His first annotations concerning the study of uranium radiation can be found in a notepad which bears in its cover: "H. Becquerel / 1894 - (Phyllis respiration) / 1896 - (mars) / Phosphorescence invisible / 1^{ères} recherches / I / 1896 / Uranium". It is evident that the notebook was first used to record some unfinished studies on chlorophyll in 1894 and then it was recycled for the registration of the new researches with uranium salts, in 1896. The eight initial sheets of the notebook contain notes concerning phosphorescence of chlorophyll in *Phyllis*, a genus of Rubiaceae. The next sheet is blank, and at the tenth leave we find the title: "1896 / Rayonnement invisible des corps phosphorescents / 1. sulfate double d'uranyle et de potasse", followed by this remark: "The first experiments were described in the Comptes Rendus, and the data are on the photographic plates" (*Les premières expériences ont été décrits dans les comptes rendus, et les indications sont sur les plaques photographiques*). There follows the description of an experiment started on March 3, that is, the day after Becquerel's second communication to the Academy of Sciences. So, Henri Becquerel's notepad does not contain any description of the experiments reported in his two first papers about uranium radiation.

Could he possibly have used another notebook when he made his first experiments? I have consulted all those that are kept at the Archive of the *Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle*, and there is no trace of those early trials. Besides that, Becquerel's remark does not refer to any other manuscript, it just points out the place where the results were published.

How can we interpret the lack of any record concerning those initial experiments? Maybe they had been made by another person – Louis Matout? – who took notes in his own notebook or in loose sheets. This issue could only be elucidated if new documents are uncovered.

5. LOUIS MATOUT'S EARLY LIFE

Let me now start the presentation of Louis Matout, paying special attention to his scientific career.

Louis-René Matout was the youngest of the two sons of the French painter Louis-Nicolas Matout (1811-1888). Louis-Nicolas became a famous artist especially for the large historic and religious wall paintings he produced for several churches, the Louvre Museum, the large amphitheater of the Paris School of Medicine, and many other places, besides many smaller paintings (Larousse, 1866-1890, vol. 17, p. 1574). Both the painter Louis-Nicolas Matout and his descendant Louis-René Matout are usually named Louis Matout, and this is a source of confusion when one attempts to find information about the son.

Louis Matout, the painter, was not a rich person. At his funeral, one of his best friends, the painter François-Louis Français (1814-1897), pronounced a speech saying:

Matout was one of those chosen natures that leave a strong imprint on minds and hearts.

Pushed towards high aspirations in the practice of his art, a tireless worker, he fulfilled his task with an energy and perseverance which should have protected his old age. Alas! It has not happened.

The family he leaves behind and loved dearly will not inherit from him a fortune, but he leaves them an honored and spotless name. (Français, *apud* Anonymous, 1888a, p. 2)

⁷ Becquerel's notebooks can be found at the Archive of the *Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle*. I was able to consult them during a very short visit, in 2003.

A few years after his passing, some of his remaining works, together with paintings and other artworks donated by friendly artists, were sold for the benefit of his widow and sons (Haro, 1892). Some of the paintings – those offered by William-Adolphe Bouguereau, Jules Adolphe Aimé Louis Breton, and François-Louis Français – were sold for the highest prices (4,000 francs, 2,300 francs, 1,420 francs, respectively),⁸ and the whole selling has probably attained over 30,000 francs. For comparison: towards the end of the 19th century, the French yearly average income was about 2,000 francs, corresponding to about US\$30,000 in current value.

Louis-Nicolas Matout was a very tall person: he belonged to the “Society of great men” (*Société des grands hommes*):

Louis Matout took part of the Society of Great Men; he was one of the last survivors. This society of great men once had brilliant days: Chenavard⁹ and Français were among them. The talent had nothing to do with it; it was the high stature that was essential. Each member of the Great Men’s Society had to be nearly six feet tall. (Anonymous, 1888b, p. 2)

Fig. 2. Louis-Nicolas Matout around 1860, by Lazerges & Dallemagne (left); Louis-René Matout, caricature made in 1906 by Georges Dupuy (right). Credits: J. Paul Getty Museum and Matout Family website.

Louis-René Matout inherited his father’s physique and his countenance (Fig. 2). His friend Sylvain Massé (1888-1971) described him as “very tall, leaning a little to put himself within earshot” (Massé, 1945, p. 2). For comparison: the height of Henri Becquerel was 1.58 m, and that of Jean Becquerel was 1.61 m, according to the information available at the *École Polytechnique* database of former students.¹⁰

When his father died, Louis-René Matout was 18 years old. I have been unable to find out any information about his education, but he probably underwent some scientific or technical training.

The earliest notice about the career of Louis-René Matout can be found in a letter written by Edmond Perrier (1844-1921), director of the *Muséum d’Histoire Naturelle*, to the Ministry of Public Instruction and Fine Arts, asking for the promotion of Matout from *Préparateur* to Assistant of the Chair of Applied Physics, in 1909.¹¹ This letter was found by Josette Fournier

⁸ Cf. the notice that appeared in the newspaper *La Liberté*, May 27, 1892, at page 3.

⁹ The painter Paul-Marc-Joseph Chenavard (1808-1895).

¹⁰ <https://bibli-aleph.polytechnique.fr/>

¹¹ *Le Directeur du Muséum d’histoire naturelle à Monsieur le Ministre de l’Instruction Publique & des Beaux-Arts. Paris, le 5 Avril 1909* (Archives Nationales, Paris, dossier F/17/24396).

and Paul Fournier at the French National Archives, and it was partly published by Bernard Bodo (Bodo, 1996, p. 46). Part of the letter is translated below:

Mr. Louis Matout worked from 1892 to 1897 in the electrical measurements laboratory of the Carpentier workshop; he took care of the calibration and, in general, of the improvements to be made to the apparatus of Physics which are used in research laboratories and in industry. In 1897, Mr. Matout was requested by Mr. Henri Deslandres to be his assistant at the Observatory of Physical Astronomy of Meudon, and he collaborated in several spectroscopy works. Afterwards, when Mr. Deslandres has undertaken a study on the Zeeman phenomenon in the spectrum of iron in common with Mr. Henri Becquerel, Mr. Matout was in charge of part of the experiments and his collaboration is mentioned in the *Comptes Rendus* of the Academy of Sciences (1898).

According to this report, four years after the passing of his father, Louis-René Matout was working under Jules Adrien Carpentier (1851-1921), in a highly technical position. Carpentier's workshop had formerly belonged to Heinrich Daniel Ruhmkorff (1803-1877). In 1878, after Ruhmkorff died, Carpentier was able to buy the workshop by a very low price, and in a few years he transformed it into a house specializing in the study and manufacture of electrical measuring instruments intended for use in scientific experiments and industrial uses. In 1878, Carpentier's workshop employed 30 men working in the premises, and 10 working outside, in the production of scientific and technological instruments, especially those associated with electricity, magnetism and electromagnetism. The profits were between 150,000 and 200,000 francs, half of this amount coming from exports (Blondel, 1988, p. 108). He worked closely with university professors such as Marcel Deprez (1843-1918) and Arsène d'Arsonval (1851-1940), manufacturing electrical devices suitable for the measurement of the heavy currents necessary for the application of electricity to industry. Christine Blondel describes the important scientific condition of Carpentier's workshop:

A former student of the École Polytechnique where he was followed the next year by Antoine Breguet – the heir to the Breguet house – he [Carpentier] hired other engineers as collaborators. H. Armagnat, the head of the “measurements office” he set up, has a solid scientific background and is the author of a high-level reference work on industrial electrical measurements. Similarly, A. Breguet, who joined the family firm as scientific director after his studies at the École Polytechnique and his military service in the Telegraphs, introduced a research laboratory. He worked there in particular with his cousin and main collaborator, Alfred Niaudet, author of the first French book on Gramme machines. The house made extensive use of young engineers in the years following Breguet's early death in 1882 and the installation of new workshops planned by the latter. (Blondel, 1988, p. 110)

Carpentier produced both small scale instruments, especially devised for research and teaching; and mass production of devices used in industry (generation, transmission and use of electricity) and communication (telegraph). Dominating the market, in the 1890s his workshop was the only one to supply the French electrical industry with all of its tools. Around 1890, Carpentier also began the production of optical apparatuses, including photographic cameras and, after 1895, cinematographic devices (Blondel, 1988, p. 114, 117). Of course, this was a highly profitable business. At the turn of the century, a professor such as Pierre Curie received between 12,000 and 15,000 francs a year; Carpentier earned about 700,000 francs (*ibid.*, p. 117).

Taking into account this information concerning Carpentier's workshop, it is possible to understand why the young Louis-René Matout might have been attracted to work there – it probably offered a good payment and it was an exciting environment where he could learn and develop his scientific and technical interests, in contact with highly competent experts.

However, according to Edmond Perrier's letter of 1909 that was cited above, "in 1897 Matout was requested by Henri Deslandres to be his assistant at the Observatory of Physical Astronomy of Meudon, and he collaborated in several spectroscopy works". It is very difficult to grasp why Matout give up his job at the workshop to work with Deslandres. What did Deslandres offer to Matout that he did not already have at the Carpentier atelier? The income of an assistant at an astronomical observatory was not very high. Henri Deslandres worked at the Paris Observatory from 1889 to 1897 (Stratton, 1954, pp. 66-67). He was appointed astronomer of the Astrophysical Observatory of Meudon on November 23, 1897 (Loewy, 1897, p. 31), but he did not assume the new position immediately. It is unlikely that he could have invited Matout to work with him before 1898.

Fig. 3. Henri Becquerel with the electromagnet used for his researches on the Zeeman effect. Public domain image, National Library of Medicine / Wikimedia, available at <http://ihm.nlm.nih.gov/images/B02617>

The biographical notices concerning Deslandres (D'Azambuja, 1948; Villat, 1948) do not describe the period of his collaboration with Becquerel at the *Muséum*. However, the timing of some publications provides temporal boundaries for that partnership. During the first half of 1897, Henri Becquerel interrupted his publications about uranium radiation (possibly because he had no expectation of obtaining new important findings in that field) and he became involved in the study of the Zeeman effect, which had been discovered in 1896. There is a famous

photograph of Becquerel proudly standing at the side of the huge electromagnet used at the *Muséum* for those experiments (Fig. 3).

Henri Becquerel's first communication on the Zeeman effect to the Academy of Sciences was made on November 8, 1897 (Becquerel, 1897). His next communication on this subject, on April 4, 1898, reported the results from his collaboration with Deslandres (Becquerel & Deslandres, 1898a). The published paper does not mention when their experiments were made, nor does it reveal the name of any person who helped them in the investigation. Their second joint communication was given on July 4, 1898. A footnote at the end of the published paper declared: "We were kindly assisted in these experiments by M. Matout" (Becquerel & Deslandres, 1898b, p. 24). This is the earliest confirmation of Louis Matout's collaboration with Deslandres and with Henri Becquerel.

Deslandres' earlier publications do not mention Louis Matout, although they do reveal the names of several people who participated in his researches: "Those researches were done with the help of my two assistants, Millochau and Mittau" (Deslandres, 1897a, p. 949); "These researches were carried out in the Spectroscopy Laboratory of the Observatory, with the assistance of Mr. Landrin, graduate of science, and Mr. Millochau, assistant astronomer" (Deslandres, 1897b, p. 1300). "The mission sent by the Bureau des Longitudes, and consisting of Mr. Deslandres, of the Observatory of Paris, of Mrs. Millochau and Mittau, assistants, and Mr. Coculesco, Romanian astronomer, seconded to the mission, established itself at the same point as the English mission, at Foundiougue" (Anonymous, 1894, p. 241); "While Mr. Bigourdan will mainly deal with the mathematical observation of the precise moment of the contacts and the duration of the eclipse, Mr. Deslandres will deal with the spectroscopic observation. He has the help of Mrs. Millochau and Mitteau" (Anonymous, 1893).

Someone might suspect that "Mitteau" was a misspelling of "Matout", but the name appears exactly with the same letters in several different sources. Hence, it was not possible to confirm that Louis Matout collaborated with Deslandres at the Paris Observatory or at the Meudon Observatory, before he participated in the researches on the Zeeman effect at the *Muséum*.

6. LOUIS MATOUT AT THE MUSEUM

The second joint publication by Deslandres and Becquerel, referred to above, attests that Matout worked with them before July 4, 1898. The connection Deslandres / Matout / Becquerel was also described by Yves Le Grand (1908-1986), who was personally acquainted with Matout, having worked with him for many years at the *Muséum*. In an obituary for Jean Becquerel, he wrote:

For the work carried out at the Museum, he [Jean Becquerel] could count on the precious help and dedication of his collaborator Louis Matout; the latter was Deslandres' assistant and had accompanied him in 1897 when Deslandres came to the Museum to work with Henri Becquerel on the effect that Zeeman had just discovered. At the end of 1897, Deslandres was appointed director of the Meudon Observatory and Becquerel kept Matout at the Museum; there, he was appointed assistant in 1909 (today, one would say sub-Director of the Laboratory), and he kept this function until his retirement in 1934; I then succeeded him. (Le Grand, 1954-1955, p. xii)

It is likely that Yves Le Grand got this account from Matout himself, but it introduces two new puzzles. First, it points out that the Becquerel-Deslandres collaboration happened in 1897, but there is no evidence that it occurred before 1898. Second, it declares that when Deslandres was appointed director of the Meudon Observatory, at the end of 1897, "Becquerel kept Matout at the Museum". It is very hard to understand why would Matout prefer joining Becquerel and leaving Deslandres at that time. As the director of the newly founded Meudon Observatory,

Deslandres would be able to offer a significant position to Matout – if he wanted to. On the other hand, Becquerel had nothing to offer. As will be shown later, there was no vacant position at the *Muséum* and Matout was only hired as Becquerel's *préparateur* in 1901.

A talk by Jean Becquerel – Henri Becquerel's son – provided a similar date for the beginning of their collaboration:

It is a pleasant duty for me to recall that, starting from 1897, my father had as collaborator his assistant, Mr. Louis Matout, a physicist endowed with remarkable intuition and rare experimental skill. My father said he was his right hand. (Becquerel, 1939, p. 131)

Jean Becquerel was born in 1878, and therefore he was only 18 years old when his father began his studies about the radiation emitted by uranium compounds. At that time, Jean did not participate in the activities of his father's laboratory and it is therefore likely that the information he provided in 1939 about Matout was obtained indirectly – perhaps from Matout himself.

I have consulted the staff of the archive of the *Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle* concerning the beginning of Louis Matout collaboration with Becquerel, and I obtained the following reply: “The individual professional file of Louis-René Matout, preserved in the dossier AM 534 and dated 1912, indicates that he entered the Museum on March 23, 1898. First a preparer [*préparateur*] at the Museum, he served as an assistant from April 15, 1909. [...] This file does not contain more precise information on the work carried out by Louis-René Matout for Henri Becquerel”.¹²

So, according to the documents kept at the Archives of the *Muséum*, Matout started working with Becquerel in March 1898. However, he was not appointed a *préparateur* at that moment. This only occurred three years later, at the beginning of 1901, according to three different sources:

Mr. Louis-René Matout is appointed assistant [*préparateur*] to the chair of applied physics at the Natural History Museum, replacing Mr. Laugier, who has been permitted to assert his rights to a retirement pension. (Anonymous, 1901a, p. 4)

Mr. Matout (Louis-René) is appointed assistant [*préparateur*] of the chair of applied physics at the Natural History Museum (January 5). (Anonymous, 1901b, p. 377)

By decree dated January 5, Mr. MATOUT was appointed assistant [*préparateur*] of the Applied Physics chair at the Museum, replacing Mr. LAUGIER, allowed, at his request, to exercise his rights to retirement. (Anonymous, 1901c, p. 3)

What can be inferred from those contradictory sources of information? The official appointment of Louis-René Matout as *préparateur* of the chair of Applied Physics certainly occurred on January 5, 1901. However, *before that time*, it seems that he was already working there (since March 1898), possibly as a volunteer (unpaid) assistant, a position that was called “*préparateur bénévole*”.

Could Louis-René Matout have worked for several years without receiving any payment? It is unlikely that he could do so. As was shown above, after his father had died, in 1888, the family was in a difficult pecuniary situation. He was possibly well paid while he worked at Carpentier's workshop, from 1892 to 1897, but he certainly did not become rich. How could he afford working at the *Muséum* for nothing?

¹² Information provided on January 13, 2022, by Alice Laforêt, archivist, *Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle*.

I can imagine two possible situations: (1) Matout had a part-time job elsewhere and worked without payment at the *Muséum* during his free time; or (2) Henri Becquerel paid Matout as his private assistant. However, there is no evidence that either of those possibilities did occur.

Hitherto, I have been unable to ascertain the exact beginning of Matout's collaboration with Henri Becquerel, and that is a crucial information needed to assess the possibility of the claim concerning his participation in the discovery of radioactivity. The best information I was able to obtain indicate that:

- (1) From 1892 to 1897, Louis-René Matout worked in Carpentier's workshop;
- (2) In 1897 or, more likely, in 1898, he participated in the joint research of Deslandres and Becquerel on the Zeeman effect;
- (3) In 1898 he was officially admitted to the *Muséum*, without payment.

There is no evidence that Matout knew or worked with Becquerel before 1897. Besides that, up to 1901, Becquerel's *préparateur* was Prosper Laugier, and only at the beginning of 1901 Matout was officially appointed to that position. Of course, even if Matout began working with Henri Becquerel in 1897, it would be impossible for him to participate in the earliest experiments on uranium radiation, which occurred in 1896. This rules out his participation in the discovery of radioactivity.

After Henri Becquerel's passing, in 1908, Matout published a notice about him in the journal *Le Radium* (Matout, 1908). In obituaries, the authors do usually state what was their personal relationship with the subject whose life they are describing. Accordingly, we could expect to find some information about the earliest contact between Matout and Becquerel in this article, but unfortunately the notice does not provide any information about that.

Fig. 4. The Physics laboratory of the Museum of Natural History, attached to the official residence of the Becquerel family up to 1892, was operated at the so-called "Cuvier house", shown in this picture. (Photograph by Madame Chardon, March 1903. Public Domain. Source: <https://www.lookandlearn.com>, image YP0708510)

7. COLLABORATION WITH HENRI BECQUEREL

It is known that after Matout started working with Becquerel, he became an invaluable collaborator and that, furthermore, he also initiated some independent scientific work. It is possible to distinguish several different facets in Matout's career; in the first period, up to 1904, his scientific work was developed in the shadow of Henri Becquerel. Although it is difficult to distinguish his personal contribution in this period, he certainly played a relevant role in Henri Becquerel's studies on radioactivity, as described by Jean Becquerel:

On March 1, 1896, Henri Becquerel discovered radioactivity. I must add that, in his researches on this new phenomenon, my father had a collaborator: he was fond of saying that Mr. Louis Matout was his "right hand". I would like to pay tribute to the experimental skill of Mr. Matout and to the contribution he made to the progress of science. (Becquerel, 1924, pp. 565-566)

From the beginning of his work as *préparateur* to Henri Becquerel's death, in 1908, Louis-René Matout played a growing role in the planning, execution and analysis of experiments. Catherine Gaziello has studied the archival documents that disclosed this collaboration, including letters exchanged between Matout and Becquerel when the later was away from the laboratory.

As for the letters, they are almost all from Louis Matout, assistant to Henri Becquerel in the physics laboratory of the Museum. Reading them allows us to understand that Becquerel, who was absent from Paris fairly regularly,¹³ left instructions for his collaborator on the experiments to be continued or attempted in his absence, in the form of letters or loose notes inserted into the notebooks. Matout reported by letter to Becquerel what he had done and the results obtained, and he recorded on separate sheets, or even in his letters, the measurements observed. On his return, Becquerel kept these documents in their place in his notebooks so that he could then relate all the data on the same experience and prepare his communications on the subject. A closer examination of the numerical measurements reveals that certain measurements are from the hand of Louis Matout, others are written by Henri Becquerel: the name of each one is specified in front of each column of figures, undoubtedly to allow comparison of the results obtained in parallel by one and the other. In some cases, the measurements listed are obviously checks made on the measurements taken, both by Henri Becquerel and by Louis Matout.

The collaboration between the two physicists, as it appears through a simple material examination of the documents, is very different from that which existed between Cuvier and his correspondents: although it is evident that Becquerel is the one who designs the experiments to be carried out and the devices to be put in place, this in no way excludes initiatives by his assistant to improve or diversify the results. And as far as the experiments themselves are concerned, the two men work on equal terms, each validating and verifying his measurements and those of the other. (Gaziello, 1997, p. 388)

Most of Henri Becquerel's publications do not disclose Matout's contribution. The first explicit acknowledgement appeared in a paper published in 1899, on the influence of a magnetic field on the radiations of radioactive bodies: "I was kindly helped in these experiments by M. Matout" (Becquerel, 1899, p. 996). This recognition is particularly noteworthy, taking into account a part of the 1909 letter of Edmond Perrier that was cited above:

Mr. Matout also collaborated in the first attempts of identification of the new rays discovered by Mr. H. Becquerel and we must attribute to him a large part in the solution of one of the

¹³ Gaziello's explanation is not correct. Becquerel wrote frequently to Matout because he did not live in the premises of the *Muséum* or nearby, and for that reason he did not go to the laboratory on a daily basis. Until 1892, the Becquerel family lived at the so-called "Cuvier house" belonging to the *Muséum*. After the death of his father Edmond, Henri Becquerel moved with his wife and son to the Boulevard Saint-Germain, at a distance of about two kilometers from the *Muséum* (Barbo, 2003, p. 129).

fundamental problems of modern physics: that of the nature of the rays emanating from radioactive bodies. By achieving the magnetic and electrostatic deviations of these rays, he has in fact provided the data making it possible to obtain the ratio of the charge to the mass of the corpuscles.

So, according to the report presented by the Director of the *Muséum* in 1909, Matout was the main responsible for those highly important experiments. This was, probably, Matout's most important contribution to the study (but not to the discovery) of radioactivity. However, his collaboration in those fundamental experiments was not acknowledged by Henri Becquerel in his 1903 work where he presented a review of his own contributions (Becquerel, 1903).

In 1901, Becquerel published in one of his articles an account of an independent experiment made by Matout:

As a complement to the destructive action of radium radiation on organic tissues, I will also mention a series of experiments undertaken in my laboratory, by Mr. Louis Matout, on the germination of seeds exposed to radium radiation before being planted. The experiments used seeds of garden cress and white mustard. Seeds, in equal numbers, were arranged in a single layer at the bottom of two small paper cylinders closed by a thin sheet of paper; one of the cylinders was exposed to radium radiation, the other served as a control. An exposure of twenty-four hours did not significantly change the seeds; but, by prolonging the exposure up to one week or even more, the result was obtained that none of the seeds thus exposed to the radiation of radium and planted subsequently germinated, while the seeds not exposed and planted at the same time that the others have germinated on the average in the proportion of eight out of ten. This very clear result shows that the prolonged action of the radiation has destroyed in the seed the faculty of germinating. (Becquerel, 1901, p. 712)

At that time, Matout did not publish his own description of the experiments (he did so in 1904), but they became widely known and they were cited by many authors, in the following years. In the same year, Henri Becquerel and Pierre Curie published a joint paper on the physiological effects of radium rays (Becquerel & Curie, 1901). In this article, Becquerel reported that he had some skin burns because he had carried in his pocket a tube containing a radium salt. A rumor circulated that Louis Matout had warned him not to handle the radioactive substance in such a careless way, but Becquerel did not pay attention to the advice:

Like many another revolutionary discovery, the possibility of employing radium as a therapeutic agent was first suggested by an accident. Had Henri Becquerel been less scornful of his assistant, Matout, when he remarked that his superior might find a safer repository for a tube of pure radium than the pocket of his waistcoat, Becquerel would have been spared the discomfort of the burn upon the skin directly beneath that same waistcoat pocket, which about two weeks thereafter gave Matout a chance to employ the Gallic equivalent of "I told you so". But medical science might have waited much longer for this invaluable adjunct to its armamentarium. (Anonymous, 1922, p. vii)

We can find very few references to Matout's assistance to his researches in some others papers by Henri Becquerel: "I was kindly helped, in these experiments, by Mr. Matout, *préparateur* at the *Muséum*" (Becquerel, 1906a, p. 371). A similar acknowledgment can be found at the English version of the same work: "I have been obligingly assisted in the above experiments by Mr. Matout, preparation-room assistant at the Museum" (Becquerel, 1906b, p. 728).

Henri Becquerel passed away on August 25 1908. This was the end of a fruitful period of the Chair of Applied Physics at the *Muséum*, and it also marks a change in Louis Matout's career, as will be shown later.

8. MATOUT'S PUBLICATIONS UP TO 1908

Some of Louis Matout's autonomous scientific publications appeared in the journal *Le Radium*, beginning in 1904. The context in which this periodical arose is highly relevant. Henri Becquerel, Pierre Curie and Marie Curie were jointly awarded the Nobel Prize of 1903, for their contributions to the study of radioactivity. In January 1904, the chemist and industrialist Émile Arnet de Lisle (1853-1928), who had provided the Curies with facilities for the production of radium, afforded funds for the creation of the journal *Le Radium*, the first periodical publication mainly devoted to radioactivity (Herran, 2008, p. 276; Califano, 2012, p. 141). Its director was Henri Louis Marie Achille Farjas (1854-1915), an engineer with editorial experience – he had founded in 1888 the *Revue Universelle des Inventions Nouvelles*. The editor of the new journal was Jacques Danne (1882-1919), an assistant of Marie and Pierre Curie. The initial aim of *Le Radium* was to be an “instrument of popularization and research”, but it became a strictly academic journal after six months. Its editorial committee included Henri Becquerel, Pierre Curie, Ernest Rutherford, René Blondlot, André-Louis Debierne, Pieter Zeeman, Heinrich Rubens and several other outstanding researchers. The list presented below contains Louis Matout's papers published in this journal:¹⁴

- MATOUT, Louis-René. Quelques effets causés par le rayonnement du radium sur les substances organiques vivantes. *Le Radium*, **1** (6): 6-7, 1904.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. Le rayonnement du radium. *Le Radium*, **1** (7): 6-14, 1904.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. Correspondance. Note sur la phosphorescence par les rayons α . *Le Radium*, **1** (9): 96, 1904.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. Conséquences hypothétiques d'un phénomène accessoire de la radioactivité. *Le Radium*, **1** (10): 99-102, 1904.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. L'éther considéré comme élément chimique. *Le Radium*, **1**: 116-117, 1904.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. Étude sur la phosphorescence. *Le Radium*, **2**: (2) 35-43; (4) 124-130, 1905.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. Sur la valeur relative des étalons lumineux, Carcel, Hefner et Vernon Harcourt. MM. A. Perot et Laporte. *Le Radium*, **3**: 372-373, 1906.
- BELOT, Joseph ; MATOUT, Louis ; MOUTON, Henri. Exposition de la Société Française de Physique, 19-21 avril 1906. Compte rendu. *Le Radium*, **3** (7): 202-214, 1906.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. La phosphorescence cathodique. *Le Radium*, **4**: 20-27, 1907.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. La thermoluminescence et la coloration des fluorines. *Le Radium*, **4** (12): 413-415, 1907.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. Henri Becquerel (1852-1908). *Le Radium*, **5**: 289-290, 1908.

The first of the papers listed above contains Matout's own account of his experiments on the effect of radium radiation upon seeds, which had been summarized by Becquerel in 1901. Most of those papers are theoretical contributions – both popular and more specialized ones; only a few of them contain the description of original experimental research. In this respect, Matout was highly independent of Henri Becquerel, who was disinclined to anything but very restricted and technical writings.

The subject of most of those articles is related to the research themes of the *Muséum*: radiation, luminescence, etc. However, he also addressed subjects that have not been dealt with by Henri Becquerel, such as the ether as a chemical element – where he discussed a recent proposal by Dmitri Ivanovic Mendeleev (1834-1907) – and the interpretation of radioactivity as the transformation and evolution of the elements.

¹⁴ For easier consultation, Matout's publications are shown in the body of the article, and not at the bibliographical list at the end of this paper.

Louis Matout was a very active collaborator of *Le Radium*, to which he also contributed short notes in the sections on *Revue des livres*, *Revue des travaux* and *Méthodes et appareils*, from 1904 to 1910. Those short notes will not be listed here. It is relevant to remark, however, that his reviews display a very wide scientific expertise.

Besides his publications in *Le Radium*, Matout also started publishing in other journals:

MATOUT, Louis-René. La triboluminescence. *Revue des Idées: Études de Critique Générale*, 2 (18): 467-470, 1905.

MATOUT, Louis-René. Les propriétés physico-chimiques du radium. *La Presse Médicale*, 16 (29): 227-229, 1908.

9. THE MEANING OF *PRÉPARATEUR* IN THE EARLY TWENTIETH CENTURY

Louis Matout's numerous scientific publications will certainly astonish anyone who thinks that a *préparateur* was just a laboratory helper. It is important, therefore, to elucidate the meaning of this occupation at that time.

It was impossible to find any explanation about the meaning of *préparateur* in the publications of the Natural History Museum. There was probably a tacit understanding of its import, and no explicit clarification was needed. The best information I have been able to find occurred in a debate about Higher Education at the Senate of the French Republic in 1919, shortly after the end of World War I. The discussion was prompted by senator Émile de Goy (1853-1925), a physician who was deeply involved in educational issues (Goy, 1919).

In his presentation to the Senate, Émile Goy referred to the situation at the university, but the information he provided can probably be also applied to the *Muséum*, with a few changes.

At present, the normal staff of the laboratory comprises, in addition to the director, an assistant director [*sous-directeur*], who is at the same time laboratory manager, four *préparateurs* for practical work, one *préparateur* for the courses delivered by the professor and five lab boys. The lecturer is attached to the chair. [...] The number of *préparateurs* being unfortunately insufficient, we are obliged to have recourse to the goodwill of former graduate students and candidates for admission [*candidats à l'agrégation*], who agree to fulfill the functions of volunteer preparer [*préparateur bénévole*]. (Goy, 1919, p. 510)

At the *Muséum*, the Director was the Professor of the chair. The second position was that of the Assistant, or *Sous-Directeur*, who was the laboratory manager [*chef de travaux*]. The third level was that of the *préparateur* – only one paid *préparateur*, in the case of the *Muséum*, for the Chair of Applied Physics. The fourth level was that of laboratory boys (*garçons de laboratoire*), some of which had a specialized technical training.

The unpaid *prépareurs* were as competent as the official ones. They had completed their high-level education and some of them were qualified for obtaining the position of a professor, since they could be candidates for admission (*candidats à l'agrégation*).

Further relevant information was provided by Goy when he discussed the payment of the laboratory staff:

The gross salaries [*traitements bruts*] of full professors [*professeurs titulaires*] are 15,000 francs for the first class and 12,000 for the second. Those of lecturers [*maîtres de conférences*] range from 6,000 to 10,000 francs. [...] The salaries of laboratory managers [*chefs de travaux*] range from 3,500 to 5,500 francs, those of *préparateurs* from 2,500 to 4,500 francs. Both receive a supplement of 500 francs, if they are doctors of science. [...] The salaries of laboratory boys [*garçons de laboratoire*] range from 2,000 to 2,400 francs, also absolutely insufficient, given not only the increasing cost of living, but also the manual skill and intelligence that we demand of them and which would easily enable them to earn much better wages in industry. (Goy, 1919, p. 510)

Observe that both the *préparateurs* and the assistants (laboratory managers) could hold a high scientific status, because they could have already obtained the title of doctor of science. The *préparateur* was neither a technician nor an unqualified laboratory supporter. Two instances, related to the *Muséum*, will help to understand this condition.

The second member of the Becquerel dynasty at the *Muséum*, Alexandre-Edmond Becquerel (1820-1891), had already obtained his first degrees (*bachelier*) in letters and in mathematical sciences in 1837, before he became the *préparateur* of his father Antoine-César Becquerel (Jaussaud, 2004).

Another relevant instance is provided by Daniel Berthelot (1865-1927), one of the sons of the famous chemist Marcelin Berthelot (1827-1907). He obtained his first degrees (*bachelier*) in letters and in physical sciences in 1882 and 1883, and was accepted as *préparateur bénévole* at the Physics Laboratory of the Sorbonne in 1884. Only four years later he was formally admitted as a paid *préparateur*. While he was an unpaid *préparateur*, he obtained the teaching licenses in physical sciences (1886) and in natural sciences (1888). During his period as official *préparateur*, in 1891 he obtained the title of first-class pharmacist and in the same year he became a doctor in physical sciences. The next year he was admitted as assistant of the Chair of Applied Physics at the *Muséum*, under Henri Becquerel (Tassily, 1927, pp. 372-374).

10. MATOUT'S COLLABORATION WITH JEAN BECQUEREL

On July 6 1903, Jean Becquerel was nominated Assistant of the Chair of Applied Physics of the *Muséum*, in substitution of Daniel Berthelot, who had assumed a position as professor of Applied Physics at the School of Pharmacy (Perrier, 1903, p. 35). Up to this time, the 25 years old son of Henri Becquerel had never been involved in the activities of the *Muséum*. His nomination – instead of the natural appointment of Louis Matout, 34 years old, who was the expected candidate – was clearly an act of nepotism.

It is likely that Jean Becquerel received much help from Louis Matout since the beginning of his work at the *Muséum*, in 1903. Jean Becquerel's first publications, in 1904, were about Blondlot's N-rays. The scientific community soon questioned the very existence of this radiation and Jean Becquerel abandoned this area. In 1906, he began the publication of a series of papers on the Zeeman effect and other magneto-optical phenomena. He also studied the luminescence of solids at very low temperatures. Jean Becquerel's studies on N-rays were usually kindly passed over by those who described his scientific contributions, such as Louis de Broglie:

After some early works, some of which were not confirmed later, he quickly oriented himself in a direction of research which extended very exactly those followed by his great-grandfather, his grandfather and his father. At that time, the attention of physicists was particularly drawn to the study of the phenomenon discovered by Zeeman in 1896 and known as the Zeeman effect. We know that it consists of a decomposition into several lines under the action of a magnetic field of the lines normally emitted by an atom. The existence of the Zeeman effect had been predicted by Lorentz using his theory of electrons, of which it was one of the great successes. The Zeeman effect had mainly been observed with gases or liquids and it was known that it was actually much more complicated than predicted by Lorentz's theory, verified only in simple cases. As early as 1906, Jean Becquerel had the idea of systematically studying this phenomenon in the case of crystals, in particular for rare earth compounds. He was quick to notice that in this case the Zeeman effect presents characteristics that are quite different from those that we had encountered until then. In particular, we sometimes observe a shift of lines in the frequency scale by the effect of magnetic fields which is the opposite of that predicted by the theory of the normal Zeeman effect. (Broglie, 1963, p. 7)

Two papers published by Jean Becquerel in 1908 acknowledged the help he received from Louis Matout: "This device was assembled with the assistance of Mr. Matout, to whom I am happy to address my thanks" (Becquerel, 1908a, p. 684); "Those phenomena have been studied with several tubes, very skillfully built by Mr. Matout" (Jean Becquerel, 1908b, p. 1310).

Henri Becquerel passed away on August 25 1908. The next year (March 11, 1909), his son Jean Becquerel was nominated the professor of Applied Physics at the *Muséum*, thus maintaining the family tradition. Now, as he became a professor, his earlier position was vacant and on April 18 1909, Louis Matout (now 40 years old) was nominated Assistant of the Applied Physics chair, and then Mr. C. Jeanson occupied the place of *préparateur* that became available (Anonymous, 1909).

Matout maintained his collaboration with Jean Becquerel, who acknowledged his help in some of his publications:

In closing, I do not want to fail to address the expression of my deepest gratitude to Prof. Kamerlingh Onnes who kindly collaborated with me to obtain the photographs which were the origin of these observations. I would also like to thank Mr. Ivan Werlein, the competent builder who cut the crystalline blades with remarkable skill, and Mr. Matout, assistant at the Museum, whose help was invaluable to me. (Jean Becquerel, 1909, p. 150)

After a few years, Louis Matout became for the first time the coauthor of two papers published by a member of the Becquerel family:

BECQUEREL, Jean; MATOUT, Louis; WRIGHT, Mlle W. Sur le phénomène de Hall dans l'antimoine. *Comptes Rendus Hebdomadaires des Séances de l'Académie des Sciences*, **156**: 463-466, 1913.

BECQUEREL, Jean; MATOUT, Louis. Die Strahlung der radioaktiven Substanzen. Pp. 1-28, in: LAZARUS, Paul (ed.). *Handbuch der Radium-biologie und Therapie einschliesslich der anderen radioaktiven Elemente*. Wiesbaden: Bergmann, 1913.

In the case of the second of those publications, it is likely that Jean Becquerel was invited by Paul Lazarus, the editor of the *Handbuch der Radium-biologie und Therapie*, to prepare the first chapter of the book, containing a review about the radiations of radioactive substances. Instead of writing the paper by himself, Jean Becquerel asked Matout to help him. At this time, the growing scientific status of Matout at the *Muséum* was quite clear.

Many years later, Jean Becquerel recalled his relationship with Matout:

It is a pleasant duty for me to recall that, starting from 1897, my father had as collaborator his assistant, Mr. Louis Matout, a physicist gifted with remarkable intuition and rare experimental skill. My father said he was his right hand. Promoted to Deputy Director [*sous-Directeur*], he was also for me the most valuable collaborator and friend whose great devotion has never wavered during the 37 years he spent at the Laboratory. He is with us today and I ask him to find here the expression of my deep affection. (Becquerel, 1939, p. 131)

Notice that Matout was Henri Becquerel's *préparateur*, not assistant, as Jean Becquerel declared. Remark, too, that he was explicitly described as a physicist [*physicien*], a title that emphasizes his scientific status.

11. MATOUT'S PUBLICATIONS AFTER 1909

After he became the Assistant of the Chair of Applied Physics, Louis Matout continued to publish some independent papers:

- MATOUT, Louis-René. Les propriétés physiques des rayons ultra-violet. *La Presse Médicale*, **18** (4): 25-26, 1910.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. Qu'est-ce que la matière? *La Presse Médicale*, **18** (97): 909-911, 1910.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. Allumage légal. *La Nature, Revue des Sciences et de leurs Applications aux Arts et à l'Industrie*, **39** (1960): 42-43, 1910.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. L'évolution de la matière dans l'univers. *La Presse Médicale*, **19**: 1015-1017, 1911.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. Le cycle d'évolution de la matière. *La Nature, Revue des Sciences et de leurs Applications aux Arts et à l'Industrie*, **39** (2005): 345-347, 1911.
- MATOUT, Louis-René. Allumettes. Vol. 1, pp. 85-98, in: BLAIZOT, Denis (ed.). *Le Monde et La Science*. Par les maîtres de la science. Paris: Schwartz & Cie., [1911].
- MATOUT, Louis-René. L'électro-aimant du Muséum. *La Nature, Revue des Sciences et de leurs Applications aux Arts et à l'Industrie*, **42** (2128): 241-243, 1914.

This list of papers certainly does not include all of his publications, that were scattered in several different journals and are difficult to track down. Around 1910, Louis Matout published two small books on radioactivity and on X-rays:

- MATOUT, Louis-René. *Les rayons X*. (Bibliothèque Scientifique des Écoles et des Familles N° 57). Paris: Gautier, [c. 1910].
- MATOUT, Louis-René. *Le radium*. (Bibliothèque Scientifique des Écoles et des Familles N° 85). Paris: Gautier, [c. 1910].

These books were part of a collection organized by Henri Gautier (1855-1938) with the aim of bringing to a wider public the new advances of science of that time.

During this period, Louis Matout collaborated with Paul Becquerel (1879-1955), a biologist who was Henri Becquerel's nephew. Paul Becquerel was interested in the hypothesis that life on Earth had originated from other planets, through the transportation of spores and seeds through space. This could only occur if the spores and seeds could withstand the conditions of vacuum, extremely low temperature and radiation in outer space (Raulin-Cerceau, 2004, p. 24). With the help of Matou, Paul Becquerel tested the effect of ultraviolet radiation on spores and seeds and concluded that they could not survive those conditions. In his report,¹⁵ Paul Becquerel did not acknowledge the collaboration of Matout. However, in a paper he published the next year about the origin of life, Louis Matout described their joint experiments.

- MATOUT, Louis-René. Sur l'origine de la vie. *La Nature, Revue des Sciences et de leurs Applications aux Arts et à l'Industrie*, **39** (1972): 238-239, 1911.

12. MILITARY RESEARCHES

The beginning of World War I had, of course, a strong impact on scientific researches. Jean Becquerel and Louis Matout participated in military research, during the war:

I cannot conclude this analysis of the works of Jean Becquerel without saying a word about those he did, in the service of national defense, during the war of 1914-18. Mobilized at the start of the war as a captain of territorial engineering, he was attached to the military government of Paris and he was responsible for directing various construction works in the Paris region. Then, in October 1915, when scientific research for national defense began to be organized, Mr. Edmond Perrier, Director of the Museum and then President of the Academy of Sciences, had him appointed to be one of those who would take care of this research. From then on, he worked

¹⁵ BECQUEREL, Paul. L'action abiotique de l'ultraviolet et l'hypothèse de l'origine cosmique de la vie. *Comptes Rendus Hebdomadaires des Séances de l'Académie des Sciences*, **151**: 86-88, 1910.

mainly for the Navy in his laboratory at the Museum and in Toulon. With the help of Mr. Matout who was for a long time his Assistant and devoted collaborator, he developed an optical signaling system between ships allowing the secret transmission of Morse signals. This lightweight device, not bulky, very practical to use at sea, made a notable improvement on the already existing devices, in particular with regard to the range of the communications. He also did a lot of research on underwater microphones, an issue that was then very important. He perfected new types of these microphones and, having perfected them little by little, he obtained very interesting results. Thus, in these somewhat particular fields of research, he was also able to show his qualities as an informed physicist and skillful experimenter. (Brogie, 1963, p. 14)

Louis de Broglie's account is not altogether clear, but it seems that Matout participated in both technical developments (optical signaling system and underwater microphones).

13. AFTER THE WAR: ANGLING STUDIES

In the decade of 1920, Louis Matout became deeply involved in the study of fishes and fishing. One may wonder whether the war produced in him a temporary disenchantment with scientific investigations. However, his studies concerning fishes should also be included among his researches, although in a different field. Indeed, his earliest presentation about the new fishing method he contrived was presented in a lecture at the *Société Nationale d'Acclimatation de France* :

Mr. Matout, assistant at the Natural History Museum, gave a very curious lecture on a way of constructing the floating line based on the tactile sense of the fishes. Mr. Matout, contrary to the majority of anglers who fish without leaving a routine that is often disastrous for them, has endeavored to study the tactile sense of the fish, or, to put it better, this additional sense whose organ is a sensitive line running from the gills to the beginning of the tail at about equal distances from the backbone and the belly, and directly connected to the spinal cord. One of its functions is to detect the slightest vibrations produced by solid bodies moving in the surrounding water. Taking this into account, the systems containing a float emerging from the water, when the surface of the water enters into agitation, will have the result of making the whole line vibrate and putting to flight the fish warned by his lateral line. It is therefore necessary to cancel any resistance or, rather, to build a line offering the minimum of resistance. This is achieved by the total immersion of the float and the making of a line as smooth as possible, weighted on its largest part by a series of very small sinkers. [...] On a question from Mr. Debreuil, Mr. Matout tells us that with his fishing system, we catch, on average, four times more fishes than with the ordinary system. (Crépin, 1921, pp. 41-42)

Many years later, his son Louis-Pierre Matout reported they were fishing together when the father observed an unexpected behaviour of fishes, that led him to try different sorts of fishing line (Matout, 1946, p. 7). He afterwards obtained the help of Louis Roule (1861-1942), a specialist on reptiles and fishes of the *Muséum*, who had published both technical and popular books on fishes, including his 1914 book *Traité raisonné de la pisciculture et des pêches*.

Fig. 5. The usual floating line and its disadvantages, according to Louis Matout: (a) floater moves due to the motion of the water, and the plumb offers a strong resistance to the motion produced by the fish; (b) and (c): the waves or ripples entail a vertical motion of the line that will disturb the fishes (*Très Sport* (31): November 01, 1924, p. 17).

Fig. 6. The new “sensible line”, according to Louis Matout: (a) the immersed floater offers little resistance to the motion of the water; (b) the plumb offers little resistance to the motion produced by the fish; and (c) the motion of the waves or ripples will not entail a vertical motion of the line (*Très Sport* (31): November 01, 1924, p. 18).

Matout’s first popular publication about this subject appeared in 1924:

MATOUT, Louis. *Méthode nouvelle de pêche pratique. Comment réussir de grosses pêches.* Paris: Hachette, 1924.¹⁶

This small book produced an immediate impact and it was reviewed in many newspapers – sometimes with an exaggeration of Louis Matout’s scientific status, as in the notice that appeared in *L’Intransigeant*:

How a doctor of science, laboratory head, great physicist goes fishing for dart and bleak, chub and dace.

¹⁶ This book was reprinted several times by Librairie Hachette, up to 1943.

Mr. Louis Matout, doctor of science and great physicist, practices line fishing for his rest. He arrived to this, like many others, just by the desire of being alone with himself, in these days when the only bearable chatter is that of the river grumbling at the stones, and at the grass of the bank.

Being a man of science, Mr. Matout could not long resign himself to fishing like everyone else, because such it is the penance of those who are learned – to remain so in the face of the smallest things.

One evening when the fish had sulked in front of the bait, he wanted to know the reasons for this inappetence, and the explanations found by him, he sentenced himself to put them in a book, because this is also one of the burdens of scientists – never to keep the discoveries they have made to themselves. This book is entitled *New method of practical fishing*.

All fishermen will buy it, because no “lineman” can resist the desire to buy a fishing book, even if he is convinced in advance that he has nothing new to learn from it. [...]

I am not going to say that it will revolutionize the angler's mount; but it will have its small effect there.

Suppose someone comes to say to you, to you who seek above all things the invisibility of your line: “All that is perhaps useful, but it is not essential, at least for coarse fishing; there is better to do and otherwise.” What will you answer? “Crazy!” you will shout. Well, that's what Mr. Louis Matout tells you from the height of his science and his experiences...

But, wait before shouting “crazy”. When you have read the chapter on the causes of the inappetence of fishes; the chapter on hearing, smell, and sight of fishes; the chapter on the lateral line organs of the fishes which make its whole body the most powerful of microphones; the chapter on the *sensible line*, opposed to the *invisible line*; maybe you won't want to scream “crazy” anymore...

[...] The sensitive line is a line which, by the position of its float, the arrangement of its sinker, and the nature of its mount, offers the least buoyancy resistance, the least resistance to being dragged by the fish, least inertial resistance... This is not very clear? Obviously, the details are missing. But here is another formula: “the sensitive line is the one that comes closest to the ideal way of presenting the bait to the fish, that is to say, as if it were free, left to the current, with nothing holding it...”

I have fifteen years of river practice, traditions, routines, inherited or acquired processes, to which I hold as to my Principles; but nevertheless I am building a “sensitive line”... (Anonymous, 1924, p. 4)

This long citation is useful for showing not only the main contents of Louis Matout's book, but the surprise and amazement of an experienced fisherman who read the book.

Besides the book, Louis Matout also published short popular accounts of his new technique in newspapers and popular magazines, such these:

MATOUT, Louis-René. Les lignes flottantes: leur emploi, leur construction. *Très Sport* (31): 17-18, November 01, 1924.

MATOUT, Louis-René. Science et pêche à la ligne. *La Nature*, 52 (2632): 168-174, 1924.

A few years later, it was possible to buy a ready-made “Matout sensible line”, and also a special fishing rod developed by him, “at all good fishing equipment shops” (Figs. 7, 8).

Matout also collaborated with the annual publication *Almanach de la pêche*, published by La Renaissance du Livre from about 1927 to 1935. He eventually became the director of the publication. Louis Matout wrote several other books about angling. They were very successful.

MATOUT, Louis-René. *Pêches au coup. Nouvelle école*. 2nd edition. Paris: Roger Baer, 1932.

MATOUT, Louis-René. *L'art de trouver une bonne place à la pêche*. Paris: Baer et Schmitz, [1935].¹⁷

¹⁷ This booklet was provided free of charge to those who would send the advertisement shown in Fig. 8 to Baer et Schmitz, who produced the Matout sensible line and the Matout fishing rod.

MATOUT, Louis-René. *La pêche du gardon*. Paris: Hachette, 1938.

MATOUT, Louis-René. *La pêche moderne à la ligne flottante et la pêche au coup*. Paris: Baer et Schmitz, 1939.

MATOUT, Louis-René. *Ce que tout pêcheur doit savoir sur les poissons, pour comprendre les vraies règles de la pêche*. Paris: Hermann, 1942.

MATOUT, Louis-René. *La pêche de la carpe*. Paris: Hachette, 1943.

MATOUT, Louis-René. *Pêches banales et pêches sportives des poissons carnassiers: brochet, perche, truite, chevenne, anguille*. Paris: Flammarion, 1946.

Some of those works have undergone several editions. The last one was published posthumously, since Louis Matout died in 1944.

Fig. 7. One of the earliest advertisements of the “Matout sensible line” for fishing: “Sensitivity, the secret for results. The lines designed, executed according to the instructions and under the supervision of Mr. L. Matout are available to fishermen” (newspaper *L’Intransigeant*, June 6, 1928, p. 6)

Fig. 8. Advertisement of the « Matout sensible line” and of his fishing rods: “More than 150,000 fishermen use the L. Matout sensible line... and they catch fish! Try it, and you will perform as they do. Also request the rods pirate, ideal, Matout, champion. Your will be amazed.” (newspaper *Le Petit Journal*, June 15, 1935, p. 7)

14. MATOUT’S LAST SCIENTIFIC CONTRIBUTIONS

After World War I, Louis Matout personal scientific publications waned, except for his studies about fishes and fishing. However, up to his retirement in 1934, and even after this occasion, Louis Matout continued to cooperate with Jean Becquerel in his researches. We can find an acknowledgment of Matout’s collaboration in some of Jean Becquerel’s publications of this period:

I would like to express my sincere thanks to Mr. Louis MATOUT, Deputy Director of the Physics Laboratory at the Museum, whose assistance was invaluable to me in setting up the device and carrying out the experiments. (Becquerel, 1928, p. 345)

Mr. Matout, Deputy Director of the Laboratory, an experimenter of rare skill, and capable of overriding the lack of material resources by his ingenuity, found a process that allowed the preparation of absolutely homogeneous rare-earth glasses, which made it possible to carry out the experiments mentioned above; he prepared them himself at the Laboratory, when no manufacturer accepted to undertake this work. (Becquerel, 1929, p. 48)

The last individual paper authored by Matout was a contribution to history of science: MATOUT, Louis-René. Lamarck météorologiste. *Archives du Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle*, [series 6] 6: 45-48, 1930.¹⁸

In 1931, Louis Matout was the coauthor of three papers published by Jean Becquerel:

¹⁸ This paper was published in a special issue of the *Archives du Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle* containing papers in celebration of the first centenary of Lamarck’s death.

- BECQUEREL, Jean; MATOUT, Louis-René. Sur un nouvel effet magnéto-optique: pouvoir rotatoire suivant l'axe optique de certains cristaux uniaxes dans le voisinage des bandes d'absorption sur l'action d'un champ magnétique normal à cet axe. *Comptes Rendus Hebdomadaires des Séances de l'Académie des Sciences*, **192**: 937-939, 1931.
- BECQUEREL, Jean; MATOUT, Louis-René. Sur les effets combinés du champ électrique interne d'un cristal uniaxe et d'un champ magnétique normal à l'axe optique. Variation des composantes de bandes d'absorption du spectre ordinaire suivant les orientations relatives de la vibration incidente, des axes binaires et du champ magnétique. Polarisation circulaire et pouvoir rotatoire magnéto-électrique. *Comptes Rendus Hebdomadaires des Séances de l'Académie des Sciences*, **192**: 1091-1093, 1931.
- BECQUEREL, Jean; MATOUT, Louis-René. Sur la décomposition par un champ magnétique transversal des bandes d'absorption du xénotime. Conditions de symétrie en relation avec la symétrie cristalline. Nouvelle interprétation de l'effet magnétoélectrique. *Comptes Rendus Hebdomadaires des Séances de l'Académie des Sciences*, **193**: 158-161, 1931.

On April 21 1934, when he was 65 years old, Louis Matout retired from the *Muséum* (Gravier, 1934, p. 327) and Yves-Jacques Le Grand (1908-1986) assumed the position of Assistant and *sous-directeur*. However, Matout remained attached to the laboratory of Applied Physics as *sous-directeur honoraire*. This special title was assigned to some, but not to all, the Assistants of the *Muséum* after their retirement. In 1936, for instance, there were only 8 *sous-directeurs honoraires* in the *Muséum*, besides Matout (Anonymous, 1936). After his retirement, in 1937, he was awarded the title of *Chevalier de la Légion d'Honneur* (Berlioz, 1937, p. 169). In his position of *sous-directeur honoraire*, he continued to collaborate with Jean Becquerel until his passing, in 1944. Unfortunately, as he died during World War II, in the period when France was occupied by the Germans, only his friend Sylvain Massé published a short notice after his passing away (Massé, 1945).¹⁹ I reproduce below a full translation of his personal tribute to Louis Matout:

Louis Matout is dead. The disappearance of this man of heart dismays all those who knew him and the entire fishing world.

I met Louis Matout twenty years ago, shortly before the publication of his *Nouvelle méthode de pêche pratique*, the first of his books, which was to revolutionize and renew the art of fishing.

Twenty years of a warm friendship followed, the imprint of which I will keep until the end of my days and about which I will never be able to think of without tenderness. Because, for the good and generous Louis Matout, friendship was a bond similar to the love of a father or the affection of a brother.

I have never found him anything but understanding and welcoming, ready for any form of devotion, without regard for his already faltering old heart of which he asked so much, always convinced, whatever he did, that he could have done better, constantly blaming and apologizing for not having done more.

Very tall, leaning a little to put himself within earshot, inexhaustible, rapid but whispered speech and as if a little out of breath, clear eyes beaming with kindness, measured gestures slowed down by a kind of restraint, an obvious shyness out of simplicity, an exquisite freshness of thought and purpose, the naivety of a man of the laboratory astonished and delighted..., such

¹⁹ Sylvain Massé (1888-1971) was a post-office clerk. He and his brother Ludovic Massé (1900-1982) belonged to the group of "proletarian writers" sponsored by Henry Poulaille (1896-1980) in the 1930s through his monthly magazine *Prolétariat* (Chevandier & Henrisey, 2002, p. 221). Besides writing about his job, Sylvain published many papers and a few books about fishing. With the collaboration of his brother, he published in 1938 a "nature book and river poem" with the title *Lam, la truite, contes et romans pour tous* – a book that has been recently reprinted.

appeared to me Louis Matout when he was about fifty. I did not have to correct this first vision. I have not seen him otherwise.

He was a curious and cultured mind. His training, his profession, his missions, the daily intercourse with eminent men such as the great Pierre Curie, of whom he spoke with great emotion, Becquerel, Louis Roule, had led him to a meticulous intellectual functioning. He was detached from our earthy world, and his marked taste for abstraction seemed to lead him to metaphysics, while he remained a physicist constantly clinging to experimental proofs. Despite this professional disposition which confined him, his microscope, his cultures, his notations and his calculations, in the world of matter, there was no spirit less materialistic than his. I have never found, in the thousand letters of his rapid writing, launched in the impetus of improvisation, a single materialistic, vulgar remark – what am I saying, vulgar? – any banal or insignificant statement. Likewise, I did not discover there any other faith than the belief in human perfectibility.

He was one of those men who make the most atheists hope that not everything dies and that one day we will meet again.

His last letters testified to a courageous renunciation: “You have to submit. It's the common law,” he said, speaking of old age and the failings that cause it, perhaps thinking of imminent death.

I am quite certain that he detached himself from life without rebellion, with the serenity of the hardworking man who has fulfilled his mission well.

One does not die, one survives, especially when one has dispensed kindness and devotion around oneself.

You are still here, dear Louis Matout, you live with us as before, you will live with our children who know you, our grandchildren who will know you, you will live after them in the indelible trace of your work as a good man. (Massé, 1945, p. 2)

15. THE CLAIM CONCERNING MATOUT AND THE DISCOVERY OF RADIOACTIVITY

Let us now return to the question presented at the beginning of this paper. Did Louis Matout discover radioactivity? Or, more specifically, was he responsible for some of the initial experimental findings that Henri Becquerel described in his 1896 papers?

We have seen that Louis-Pierre Matout, the son of Louis-René Matout, did claim that his father was responsible for one fundamental move in the discovery of radioactivity, in March 1896. It is likely that Louis-René Matout himself have told this version to his family. Nowadays, the website of the Matout family (www.matout.fr) conveys the claim in the following manner:

Louis René MATOUT (1869-1944), physicist, assistant to Professor Henri BECQUEREL at the National Museum of Natural History, shared with him the discovery of radioactivity on March 1, 1896 and the amount of his share of the 1903 Nobel Prize in Physics. He devoted to radioactivity his first publications, “Le Radium” and “Les Rayons X”, followed by a dozen of others, no longer as a scientist, but as an author related to angling, and inventor of the eponymous fishing line. He was designated Academy Officer (1904), Public Instruction Officer (1910), and he was named Knight of the Legion of Honor on March 25, 1937.²⁰

This account adds a new contention: that Henri Becquerel shared his part of the 1903 Nobel Prize in Physics²¹ with Louis-René Matout. If this did occur, then the fact would be a very

²⁰ “Louis René Matout (1869-1944)”. Available at:

<http://www.matout.fr/?page_id=245>. Accessed on January 5 2022. The pages of the site of the Matout family have been crawled and kept at the Internet Archive (Wayback Machine), where their content can also be retrieved.

²¹ It is well known that the 1903 Prize was split between Henri Becquerel and the Curie couple (Marie and Pierre).

strong argument for the claim concerning Matout's participation in the discovery of radioactivity, because it would be very hard to offer an alternative explanation for Becquerel's attitude. I have contacted the Matout family and I have asked them to provide any extant evidence that the sharing of the Nobel Prize did occur. Unfortunately, they could provide no document to support that contention.

Of course, the lack of documental evidence is not a proof that the division of the prize did not occur. Until new support is uncovered, however, there is no reason to accept that it happened.

The other crucial point concerning the presumed participation of Louis-René Matout in Henri Becquerel's early experiments is, of course, the unclear timing of the beginning of their collaboration. Hitherto, it was impossible to find any evidence that Matout was already working at the *Muséum* in 1896. Detailed information about the life of Louis Matout before 1898 would be highly relevant. Once more, lack of evidence is no proof that Matout was not there. Until new evidence is found, however, there is no reason to accept that he has participated in those early experiments.

There remains the possibility that relevant documents will be found, confirming the Matout claim. We do know that Louis-René Matout kept with him, at least until the decade of 1930, many documents concerning his work at the *Muséum*, including letters he received from Henri Becquerel (Gaziello, 1997, p. 388, footnote 3). If Matout's claim is accurate and if there was any document supporting that contention, it is very likely that such documental evidence would be kept by him. Part of Matout's documentation, including 238 letters he received from Henri Becquerel, are since 1960 in the possession the Houghton Library, at Harvard University.²² Those letters were written by Becquerel from September 1899 to July 1908 and, therefore, they do not include any correspondence written in 1896. Even so, they should be carefully examined in search of retrospective information concerning Becquerel's early experiments. This is just one instance of records that could provide additional information.

The Archive of the *Muséum* might also contain some relevant documents. In a short visit I made in 2003, I could only examine a very small part of the Henri Becquerel collection. After my return to Brazil, I asked for some additional help from the archivists but, unfortunately, I received no reply. Sadly, I was unable to return to Paris to consult further documents.

As was anticipated at the beginning of this paper, it was impossible to provide conclusive evidence concerning Louis Matout's role in the discovery of radioactivity; and a description of his scientific career. A conclusive assessment of his contribution must be postponed, waiting for the discovery of further documents.

16. FINAL COMMENTS

Independently of the issue of Louis Matout's participation in the discovery of radioactivity, the examination of his life and works is highly relevant, as it provides a different view of the scientific activity, from the perspective of a competent researcher who did not become famous. This paper provides just a starting point for further studies. The exhaustive analysis of the exchange of letters between Henri Becquerel and Louis Matout would be a specially interesting undertaking, and it will require the comparison between the letters from Becquerel to Matout that are now at the Houghton Library of Harvard University, and Matout's letters to Becquerel, which are kept at the Archive of the *Muséum*. It would be particularly relevant to analyse the letters between them in the period when they studied the deflection of α and β rays in magnetic and electric fields, to check Edmond Perrier's 1909 report about the importance of Matout's contribution in this specific case.

²² MS Fr 188, Houghton Library, Harvard University. Permalink: <<http://id.lib.harvard.edu/alma/990091687710203941/catalog>>

The study of the large number of letters between Louis Matout and Henri Becquerel is a unique opportunity of obtaining a fairly detailed view about the collaboration between two researchers, during several years of joint investigations.

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